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Report on outreach to European countries without LEAPS facilities

Introduction

Synchrotrons and free electron lasers (FELs) are very potent machines that allow experiments that are often impossible to do using conventional facilities. Researchers, both academic and industrial, sometimes can do mail-in or remote measurements, but more often than not, they need to come to the LEAPS facility to do their experiments by themselves. When such a facility is not present in the researcher's home country, this can be regarded as a significant roadblock to using the LEAPS facility. Moreover, many researchers do not know they can use synchrotrons and FELs,

especially if they do not have such a facility in their country. Hence, it is crucial to perform outreach actions educating a broad spectrum of professionals about the possibilities of doing measurements at synchrotrons and FELs.

Even though there are quite a few synchrotrons and FELs in Europe, there are still noticeable gaps in the coverage across EU countries. The map above visualises the EU member states and candidates that do not have any LEAPS facilities. It is not possible to organise a dedicated workshop in each of them. After analysis of the possible countries, two were chosen to target: Greece, with the activity led by the SOLARIS team, and Ireland, led by the Diamond team, each with a different goal. This approach ensured the outreach would cover as broad an audience as possible.

Greece as a Target Market

Looking at the map above, two significant EU regions lack LEAPS facilities: the Baltic states and Balkan countries. These regions primarily require thorough and widespread information on the possibilities of doing measurements and getting access to LEAPS facilities rather than addressing a specific market sector. The outreach action described herein aimed to inform and educate as many professionals in one of these regions as possible.

Effective broad outreach requires a local “anchor”, the best one being a big conference or exhibition that brings together both academic and industrial actors. After searching through the available events, the Nanotechnology in Greece brought the biggest attention. It is a series of four scientific conferences (ISFOE24 “Symposium on Flexible Organic Electronics”, NN24 “Conference on Nanosciences and Nanotechnologies”, I3D24 “Conference on 3D Printing, AI and Manufacturing”, and ISSON24 “Summer School on Nanotechnologies”), exhibition space (EXPO), and business events (BUSINESS FORUM, Matchmaking Event) organised by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. It is one of the largest technology, networking and matchmaking annual events in Greece and the Balkan region.

Ireland as a Target Market

The other goal was to promote synchrotrons and FELs to a specific market sector within a different part of Europe.

Ireland has a thriving pharmaceutical ecosystem, a sector which has traditionally made use of research infrastructures for drug discover but less so for manufacturing. Exploring this new segment of the market in a country without this kind of facility was identified as a strong option for the task and for promoting the research capabilities offered by LEAPS members.

Pharmaceutical Ecosystem

Ireland boasts a robust pharmaceuticals ecosystem, being the largest exporter of pharmaceuticals globally. With over 85 pharmaceutical companies operating in the country, including 9 of the top 10 global pharmaceutical companies, Ireland presents a significant opportunity for collaboration and research promotion.

Strategic Advantages

- **Industry Presence:** The presence of major pharmaceutical companies provides a ready market for our research capabilities.
- **Economic Impact:** Ireland's strong export performance in pharmaceuticals underscores the potential economic benefits of targeting this market.

Workshops for regions without access to their own local light source facilities

Greek engagement

As stated earlier, the Balkans require mostly promotion of the capabilities of LEAPS. This was done through engagement in the Nanotextology 2024 event in Thessaloniki, Greece.

SOLARIS representatives participated in a variety of activities at the event. They staffed an exhibition booth at the EXPO, participated in one-on-one talks at the Matchmaking event, delivered a 15-minute presentation about synchrotrons at the BUSINESS FORUM, and presented research from SOLARIS at NN24 in the form of an invited talk.

The event was very fruitful, with many talks with the representatives of both scientific and industrial environments. SOLARIS representatives were unable to take notes about each speaker but from the notes gathered, it is certain that they got in direct contact with at least 62 people from 20 different countries: Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Izrael, Latvia, Northern

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Macedonia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Saudi Arabia, Slovenia, Spain, and the USA. 25 people were the representatives of the industry, while 41 represented academia (some had dual affiliations with both academia and industry). 31 participants originated from countries that do not have a local source of synchrotron radiation, out of which 21 were from the Balkan region (Greece, Northern Macedonia, Romania, Slovenia). The most numerous group was of Greek origin. The table and map present more detailed information.

	Industrial affiliation	Academic affiliation
Countries with synchrotrons	12	17
Countries without synchrotrons	13	22
just Balkan region	9	14

It is important to note that this data comes only from the recorded talks. We estimate that the true number of direct meetings was around 80, and around 150 people listened to the presentations. According to the organiser, around 400 people were present at the conference.

The main goal of SOLARIS’s presence at the conference was to showcase the possibility of using light sources for people from countries that do not have access to such sources. The talks with researchers and industry representatives from the Balkan region were crucial as most of them had never heard of the synchrotrons or FELs. When educated about light sources and the possibilities of accessing LEAPS facilities, they were highly interested in finding more information and, possibly, becoming users of one of the synchrotrons.

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Considering the insufficient level of knowledge and information regarding research opportunities provided by light sources among representatives of Southern European countries, it is recommended that informational activities be strengthened in this region. This could be achieved, in particular, through initiatives aimed at fostering a culture of utilising large-scale research infrastructures.

Irish engagement

Initial Research and Key Areas

We initially researched the core areas of activity for the pharmaceutical industry in Ireland and identified three main regions of concentration: Dublin, the South-west, and the North-west.

Engagement with Key Players

Following a review of funding models and key players, and consultations with Michael Ryan, the Divisional Head of International at Science Foundation Ireland and an Executive Board Member of the European Strategy Forum to Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), we approached several key organisations supporting the pharmaceutical industry in Ireland:

- **Science Foundation Ireland Research Centre for Pharmaceuticals (SSPC)**
- **Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Technology Centre (PMTC)**
- **National Institute for BioProcessing Research and Training (NIBIRT)**

Strategic Meetings and Recommendations

Diamond representatives met with all three organisations and were advised that the most effective way to promote the LEAPS industry services to the pharmaceutical sector would be to leverage existing channels to raise awareness and establish trust. This led to Diamond's participation in two significant events in Limerick, resulting in positive outcomes.

Event 1: PMTC Knowledge Day – 30 May 2024

Attendance at PMTC Knowledge Day facilitated valuable networking opportunities with 160 delegates, including key pharmaceutical companies. It culminated in a face-to-face meeting with PMTC representatives to explore synergies and capabilities, establishing a closer working relationship between PMTC and LEAPS.

The discussions with PMTC led to the signing of a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) between the University of Limerick and Diamond to allow for more detailed discussions on potential collaborations.

Event 2: SSPC Symposium – 11 June 2024

During the SSPC Symposium, a presentation was delivered focusing on the LEAPS research capabilities available in physical sciences and formulations to 178 delegates from both industry and academia from across Ireland. This approach aimed to align with the strong pharmaceutical manufacturing industry presence in Ireland.

Following our presentation at the SSPC conference, we were approached by several potential users, which has resulted in beamtime proposals to Diamond in the first instance.

During both events, we established highly productive connections with key players in the Irish pharmaceutical industry. We will continue fostering these relationships and with the aim of partnering as LEAPS with these institutes in future grant funding opportunities.

Summary

This report outlines outreach efforts aimed at European countries without access to their own synchrotrons or free electron lasers (FELs), specifically focusing on Greece and Ireland. The initiative aimed to raise awareness about the capabilities of LEAPS facilities while fostering collaborations with academic and industrial stakeholders. By targeting Greece as a representative of the Balkan region and Ireland with its pharmaceutical industry prominence, these efforts addressed diverse needs, ranging from general education to sector-specific engagement.

The initiative highlighted a significant lack of awareness about light sources among researchers and industries in the Balkan region. Educational activities were met with substantial interest, especially from Greek stakeholders. On the other hand, engagement in the Irish market resulted in collaborative discussions, the signing of an NDA for future collaborative research, and the acquisition of new beamtime users. These activities successfully promoted the potential of LEAPS facilities to new audiences and paved the way for future collaborations.

To build on the progress achieved in Greece and Ireland, LEAPS should prioritize enhancing outreach efforts in regions with limited knowledge of light sources and strengthening partnerships in key industry sectors. In the Balkans, where awareness of synchrotrons and FELs is minimal, it is essential to develop tailored educational programmes and increase participation in major regional events to engage broader audiences. Collaborations with local universities and industrial networks should be established to create sustainable avenues for outreach and long-term engagement. In countries that are more aware of the synchrotrons and FELs, efforts should focus on deepening relationships with

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specific industry stakeholders, the pharmaceutical industry in Ireland being a great example. This includes expanding joint research initiatives, hosting targeted workshops, and utilizing existing agreements to initiate pilot projects. By targeting sectors like pharmaceuticals, materials science, and advanced manufacturing, LEAPS can position itself as an indispensable research partner, driving innovation and fostering collaborations across Europe.

